

Mutagenic Activity of Deltharin 2.5 EC, a Pyrethroid Insecticide, Using the Ames Salmonella/Microsome Method

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the mutagenicity of Deltharin 2.5 EC, a synthetic pyrethrin insecticide, using the short-term bacterial test of the Ames Salmonella/Microsome Assay.

Materials and Methods: In the Ames test, *Salmonella* strains TA97, TA98, TA100 and TA102 were treated with and without S9 fraction and five different doses of Deltharin 2.5 EC were administered: 100, 50, 25, 12.5, and 6.25 µg/plate. The concentrations were dissolved in distilled water for testing.

Results: According to the results, it was mutagenic against *S. typhimurium* at a dose of 100 µg /plate for strain TA97 in the presence of S9 and for strain TA98 in both the presence and absence of S9. In other applications, values close to the control group values were determined both in the absence and presence of S9 fraction, and these changes were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Consequently, restricting the use of Deltharin 2.5 EC or preferring low doses for essential use is necessary, and public awareness is essential. It is important to evaluate this substance for toxicity using methods other than the Ames test before use.

Keywords: Ames test, Deltharin 2.5 EC, Mutagenicity, Pesticide, Pyrethroids

Ames Salmonella/Mikrozom Yöntemi Kullanılarak Bir Piretroid İnektisit Olan Deltharin 2.5 EC'nin Mutajenik Aktivitesi

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu çalışma, sentetik bir piretrin insektisit olan Deltharin 2.5 EC'nin mutajenitesinin, kısa süreli bir bakteriyel test olan Ames Salmonella/Mikrozom Testi kullanılarak değerlendirilmesini amaçlamaktadır.

Gereç ve Yöntemler: Ames testinde, *Salmonella* suşları TA97, TA98, TA100 ve TA102, S9 fraksiyonu ile ve S9 fraksiyonu olmadan muamele edildi ve Deltharin 2.5 EC'nin 100, 50, 25, 12.5 ve 6.25 µg/plak olmak üzere beş farklı dozu uygulandı. Konsantrasyonlar distile su içerisinde çözülerek deney gerçekleştirildi.

Bulgular: TA97 suşu için S9 varlığında, TA98 suşu için ise hem S9 varlığında hem de yokluğunda 100 µg/plak dozunda *S. typhimurium*'a karşı mutajenik etki gözlemlendi. Diğer uygulamalarda ise hem S9 fraksiyonunun varlığında hem de yokluğunda kontrol grubu değerlerine yakın değerler belirlendi ve bu değişimler istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bulunmadı.

Sonuç: Sonuç olarak Deltharin 2.5 EC kullanımının kısıtlanması ya da zorunlu kullanımlarda düşük dozların tercih edilmesi gerekli olup bu konuda halkın bilinçlendirilmesi bir zorunluluktur. Bu maddenin kullanımdan önce Ames testi dışındaki diğer metodlarla da toksik açıdan değerlendirilmesi önemlidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ames testi, Deltharin 2.5 EC, Mutajenite, Pestisit, Piretroidler

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1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the use of chemicals is rapidly increasing, and the use of pesticides, a common choice in agriculture, has also increased exponentially. The use of pesticides for pest control has become a widespread practice worldwide, with one estimate of approximately 5.2 billion pounds of pesticides used annually worldwide [1-3]. Using pesticides recklessly can cause serious harm to the environment, public health, plants, soil, and wildlife. In the agricultural sector, residues can leave residues on fruits and vegetables, leading to the contamination of these products. Short-term exposure can cause various health problems, such as headaches and nausea, while chronic exposure can cause infertility, neurotoxicity, endocrine system problems, and cytogenetic damage [4]. Long-term exposure can lead to diseases such as liver, testicular, breast, bone, prostate, brain, and ovarian cancers, as well as leukemia. Although residue assessments have been conducted for many pesticides in Türkiye, and studies on their genotoxic potential are increasing, health risk assessment studies are still not at the desired level [5].

In recent years, pyrethroids in particular, have become the dominant insecticide class used against pests in agricultural fields, gardens, and homes, accounting for 25% of the global insecticide sector. Pyrethroids have begun to replace highly toxic and resilient organochlorine and organophosphorus pesticides. They are still frequently used to kill ticks, insects, and mosquitoes, especially in tropical areas [6,7]. The neurotoxicity of pyrethroids is generally related to their activities on the peripheral and central nervous systems, and this group of pesticides is divided into two groups, class I and class II, according to their toxicity and physical properties. While this group of pesticides primarily alters the kinetics of voltage-gated sodium channels, those in class II also target chloride channels and GABA (gamma amino butyric acid) receptors [8-11]. Deltharin 2.5 EC is also a synthetic pyrethroid insecticide and is used in the agricultural sector and to control insects in homes.

Evaluating pesticides for genotoxicity before use is crucial for both health and agricultural development, as well as raising consumer awareness. The Ames test, used to determine mutagenic and antimutagenic activity, has been shown to be over 90% effective in studies [12]. The negative effects of pesticides not only on target organisms but also on non-target organisms and their damage to ecosystems are a globally recognized fact. The increasing use of insecticides and acaricides in recent years is crucial for demonstrating potential risks to non-target organisms through the Ames test. In this context, this study aimed to evaluate the mutagenicity of Deltharin 2.5 EC, a pyrethroid insecticide frequently used in agriculture, using the Ames/Salmonella Microsome Test.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Test Strains and Chemicals

In this study, *Salmonella typhimurium* strains TA97, TA98, TA100 and TA102 were used. Of these strains, TA97 and TA98 were used to determine frameshift mutations, TA100 strain was used to determine base pair exchange

mutations, and TA102 was used to determine Ochre mutations [13]. The insecticide Deltharin 2.5 EC used in the study was purchased in commercial form from a plant protection products dealer in Afyonkarahisar. S9 fraction was commercially supplied (Sigma-Aldrich).

2.2. Method

The doses of Deltharin 2.5 EC pesticide used during the study were freshly prepared and dissolved in sterile distilled water. Five different doses of this pesticide (100, 50, 25, 12.5, and 6.25 µg/plate) were applied. The test strains used in the study were selected according to Mortelmans and Zeiger [14] and the genotypes of the strains were checked before the experiment to ensure reliability. A preliminary study was conducted before the experiment to determine the cytotoxic dose, and the doses were determined accordingly Dean et al. [15]. Positive controls, selected according to the strains, were also applied during the experiment, and the resulting values were compared with the negative control and evaluated for mutagenicity.

2.3. Determination of Cytotoxic Dose

Non-toxic doses of the applied compound were determined according to the method of Dean et al. [15] and five different non-cytotoxic concentrations were tested. To determine the lethal doses of these compounds for strains TA97, TA98, TA100, and TA102; 100 µl of bacterial culture and 100 µl of the test substance at different doses were added to 2 ml of top agar. This mixture in the tubes was added to three different nutrient agar plates, and the plates were incubated in a 37°C incubator for 24 hours. After the treatment, the average number of colonies grown on the plates was counted and compared with the negative control group to determine toxic and non-toxic concentrations. During the mutagenic activity study, experiments were conducted with doses below the toxic dose.

2.4. Ames Plate Incorporation Test

To determine the mutagenic activity of Deltharin 2.5 EC, the plate incorporation method was performed using *S. typhimurium* strains TA97, TA98, TA100, and TA102 in the absence and presence of S9 mixture [13]. The strains were kept at 37°C for 16 hours in a shaking incubator. Positive controls were also applied in parallel with the study. For analyses without the S9 fraction, 100 µl of bacterial strains and 100 µl of pesticide at different doses were added to test tubes containing 2 ml of top agar and kept in a water bath (45°C). The tubes were individually vortexed to ensure homogeneous distribution and then plated on minimal glucose agar plates, ensuring the liquid was evenly distributed across the plate.

In the second stage of the experiment for the S9 fraction in the Ames test, 500 µl of S9 mixture was added to this mixture. The liquid mixture on the petri dish was frozen with the top agar and incubated at 37°C for 48-72 hours. At the end of the incubation, the colonies that returned were recorded. The study was conducted in triplicate for each pesticide concentration, and two separate treatments were designed. The results were statistically evaluated and compared with the control group.

2.5. Statistical Analysis of Data

For statistical analysis, first the ANOVA test was applied followed by the Dunnett t-test (two-sided) using

SPSS 18.0 for Windows, and differences between data means were considered at the $p < 0.05$ level.

3.RESULTS

The effects of Deltharin 2.5 EC on TA97, TA98, TA100 and TA102 strains with or without metabolic activation are summarized in Table 1. The Ames test is based on the principle that *Salmonella typhimurium* strains that are unable to synthesize histidine through an artificial mutation undergo a second mutation with the addition of the test compound, acquiring the ability to synthesize histidine [16,17]. In the Ames assay, each applied dose is compared to a negative control group, and values that double the colony count of the control group are reported as mutagenic. If the number of colonies increases in a dose-dependent manner, this indicates that the applied substance has weak mutagenic activity [14].

Firstly, prior to the study, genotype checks were performed to determine whether the strains were mutants, and the test strains were found to have the original mutations. According to Ames et al. [16], the spontaneous conversion of mutant bacterial strains from the his⁻ to his⁺ state occurs within certain limits. These limits are 20-50 revertants/plaque for TA98, 75-200 revertants/plaque for TA97 and TA100, and 100-300 revertants/plaque for

TA102. The results of this study were found to be between these values for both strains used. Positive control values showed significant increases compared to the spontaneous mutation rate in the four strains tested. While the highest value observed was in the TA102 with S9 at 100 µg/plate concentration of Deltharin (349.24±54.47), and the lowest value was in the TA98 without S9 at 6.25 µg/plate concentration of Deltharin (38.32±3.62).

Cytotoxic doses of the pesticides tested were determined firstly. The average revertant colony numbers in negative control were 80.21±17.14 for TA97, 33.22±5.12 for TA98, 86.22±6.13 for TA100 and 304.21±32.34 for TA102 in the absence of S9 and 115.25±10.9, 51.21±5.29, 137.19±8.18 and 337.24±41.63 in the presence of S9 respectively.

The results of the present study showed that Deltharin 2.5 EC was mutagenic against *S. typhimurium* at a dose of 100 µg /plate for strain TA97 in the presence of S9 and for strain TA98 in both the presence and absence of S9. Furthermore, revertant colony numbers in all strains became stronger with the addition of S9 to the experiment.

Table 1. Mutagenicity activity of Deltharin 2.5 EC using *S. typhimurium* assay with four different strain with and without metabolic activation.

Agent	Doses (µg/plate)	No of His+ revertants/plate, mean ± SD							
		TA97		TA98		TA100		TA102	
		- S9	+ S9	- S9	+ S9	- S9	+ S9	- S9	+ S9
Deltharin	100	148.41±35.21	262.21±12.24*	82.26±6.8*	120.62±4.45*	171.21±4.26	270.22±11.51	397.25±24.41	349.24±54.47
	50	146.12±28.31	225.21±24.21	60.35±1.7	113.13±4.14	169.30±3.38	258.12±10.38	395.52±32.45	335.54±57.19
	25	137.21±32.13	221.10±42.21	52.67±2.14	102.42±2.22	145.20±5.64	244.10±9.65	320.21±12.46	336.54±54.75
	12.5	82.21±15.18	125.42±23.24	46.58±3.58	92.10±2.21	128.3±2.65	221.16±7.21	306.21±24.54	321.42±24.56
	6.25	82.35±25.10	112.45±32.25	38.32±3.62	48.17±2.47	97.32±2.43	205.42±6.32	304.47±23.75	335.21±25.46
Negative control	100	80.21±17.14	115.25±10.9	33.22±5.12	51.21±5.29	86.22±6.13	137.19±8.18	304.21±32.34	337.24±41.63
SA	10					2945.14±42.25*			
2AA	5						2352.11±35.23*		2304.26±37.64*
2AF	200		1365.25±42.47*		1095.12±16.07*				
NPD	200	1425.36±28.57*		1350.35±26.65*					
MMC	0.5							1857.35±42.65*	

4.DISCUSSION

Several epidemiological studies published over the past two decades have suggested deleterious effects of pesticides on human health, including a possible association between pesticide use and cancers such as non-Hodgkin lymphoma, leukemia, and various types of solid tumors [18, 19]. In addition, the increasing introduction of pesticides to the market in recent years and their unconscious use raises the question of whether these substances have any mutagenic or genotoxic effects. In recent years, pyrethroids,

which have found much greater use than other pesticide groups, are widely preferred in agricultural fields, gardens, and homes [20]. Due to their advantages, the use of pyrethroid insecticides, including Deltharin 2.5 EC, has become quite widespread, and studies on the biological effects of these pesticides have become current. Deltharin 2.5 EC, has become quite widespread, and studies on the biological effects of these pesticides have become current. There are numerous studies in the literature on the toxicity of pyrethroid pesticides on mammals and insects. While

pyrethroid insecticides, in particular, yield negative results in microbial toxicity tests, the results varied across different methods, and it is not possible to draw a definitive conclusion about the pesticides in this group [21-23]. The Ames test is one of the most commonly used, cost-effective, reliable, and highly valid bacterial test systems and different bacterial mutants is used (TA97, TA100, TA98, TA102, TA1535, and TA1537) derived from the parental strain *Salmonella typhimurium* LT2 through *in vitro* mutations to determine the mutagenic activity of chemical substances [13]. The basis of the Ames test is that growth and colony formation cannot occur in these strains without histidine synthesis. After treatment with the suspected chemical, the strains can produce histidine and grow to form colonies [13,24]. In this study, the mutagenic activity of Deltharin 2.5 EC was examined using the Ames test, and the results showed that strain TA97 was mutagenic only in the presence of S9 at the highest dose of 100 µg/plate, and strain TA98 was mutagenic both in the presence and absence of S9 at the highest dose of 100 µg/plate. No mutagenic activity was observed in strains TA100 and TA102. In this study, no dose-response relationship was observed because mutagenic activity appeared only at the highest concentration. Of the five different doses used in the study, mutagenic activity was observed only at the highest dose of 100 µg/plate, and different literature studies on pyrethroids report that pesticides in this group vary in terms of mutagenicity and that this varies depending on the genetic system used [22,25-30].

In the Ames assay, *S. typhimurium* strain TA98 has frameshift mutations consisting of a -1 deletion in the hisD3052 allele, and strain TA97 has a +4 duplication in the hisD6610 allele. This allele is reversible by frameshift mutagens. In strain TA100, the base pair substitution results in a CCC codon (leucine) instead of the wild-type CTC codon (proline) in the hisG46 allele. This mutation is reversible by mutagens that cause base substitutions in G-C pairs. Strain TA102 is used to detect mutations induced by agents such as oxidants, X-rays, UV, mitomycin C, and bleomycin [31]. Considering this literature, the mutagenicity of Deltharin 2.5 EC in strains TA97 and TA98 is thought to be due to frameshift mutations [31]. In the Ames test, each strain determines the probability of a different mutation. Therefore, while mutagenic activity was observed in some strains due to differences in the mechanism of action of each strain, no such activity was observed in TA100 and TA102. Pyrethroids are more specific to target organisms compared to other pesticides, and high exposure to these pesticides also causes neurotoxicity to many non-target species, including mammals [32]. Synthetic pyrethroids are potent neurotoxicants that interact with voltage-dependent sodium channels and other ion channels, affecting nerve cell function. This action causes repetitive firing of neurons, ultimately resulting in paralysis [33-35]. Similar molecular toxicity mechanisms have generally been identified in pesticide poisonings in animals, and this mechanism has been reported to be mediated particularly by voltage-sensitive sodium channels (VSSCs). These differences in pyrethroid efficacy have been attributed to the sensitivity of VSSCs to these compounds, as well as to their intrinsic

sensitivity to body temperature and metabolism [36]. In general, the detoxification efficacy of pyrethroids varies depending on the route of administration. Limited absorption and metabolism play important protective roles against pyrethroid neurotoxicity in mammalian groups [37]. Whether or not chemical substances have genotoxic effects may vary depending on various factors. The fact that test compounds cross the bacterial cell wall does not indicate that they will directly interact with DNA. In addition, even if their concentrations reach high levels in the cytoplasm, they may not form complexes with specific binding sites in the bacterial genome [38]. Literature studies have reported a significant relationship between an agent's chemical structure and its biological activity. Many different factors, such as functional groups, rings, rings, side chains, bonding positions, nature of the chemical substance, group numbers and positions within the chemical substance's structure, are important for activity [39]. Additionally, parameters such as the duration of exposure to the chemical, the cell type studied, the applied doses, the chemical's distribution within the cell, and its physicochemical properties can also be considered factors affecting the mutagenic activity of that substance [40]. Furthermore, various properties of pyrethroids, such as their shape, ring structure, basic structural and physical properties, and ester or nonester linkages, also play a significant role in their selectivity and effectiveness against insects [41]. For all these reasons, it is crucial that even pesticides belonging to the same group be evaluated for mutagenicity through a preliminary study before application. The Ames test is not only a bacterial test system but also a method that allows us to obtain information on eukaryotic organisms by using the S9 fraction used. Biotransformation by detoxification enzymes in mammals alters the mutagenicity of many chemical agents. Following biotransformation, a mutagenic compound can become inactive, while a non-mutagenic compound can become mutagenic. The fact that bacteria lack the enzyme systems that perform the detoxification mechanisms in mammals can be considered a problem for the Ames test. However, this problem is eliminated by adding detoxification enzymes isolated from mammals to the bacterial system [13].

5. CONCLUSION

In this context, although the Ames test determined that this substance causes frameshift mutations, its toxicity assessment with other test methods is also important to ensure reliable results before marketing. These products do not pose a safety concern for users and consumers if used carefully and appropriately. For these reasons, restricting the use of Deltharin 2.5 EC and preferring low doses for essential use are among the main precautions that can be taken. The Ames test is the most widely used preliminary screening test among bacterial mutagenicity tests and provides insight into the mutagenic activity of chemical substances. Therefore, before a chemical substance is released for use, it should be pretested using both this test method and other toxicity methods.

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The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Author Contributions:

¹AO : Data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project administration; software.

¹DA: Conceptualization; investigation; methodology; project administration; writing— original draft; writing— review and editing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Yamamuro, M., Komuro, T., Kamiya, H., Kato, T., Hasegawa, H., Kameda, Y. (2019). Neonicotinoids disrupt aquatic food webs and decrease fishery yields. *Science*, 366, 620–623.
- [2] Siviter, H., Bailes, E. J., Martin, C. D., Oliver, T. R., Koricheva, J., Leadbeater, E., & Brown, M. J. (2021). Agrochemicals interact synergistically to increase bee mortality. *Nature*, 596, 389–392.
- [3] Weidenmüller, A., Meltzer, A., Neupert, S., Schwarz, A., & Kleineidam, C. (2022). Glyphosate impairs collective thermoregulation in bumblebees. *Science*, 376, 1122–1126.
- [4] Baldi, I., Filleul, L., Mohammed-Brahim, B., Fabrigoule, C., Dartigues, J. F., Schwall, S., & Brochard, P. (2001). Neuropsychologic effects of long-term exposure to pesticides: results from the French Phytoner study. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 109(8), 839–844.
- [5] Moulas, C., Petsoulas, C., Rousidou, K., Perruchon, C., Karas, P., & Karpouzas, D. G. (2013). Effects of systemic pesticides imidacloprid and metalaxyl on the phyllosphere of pepper plants. *BioMed Research International*, 2013(1), 969750.
- [6] Bradberry, S. M., Cage, S. A., Proudfoot, A. T., & Vale, J. A. (2005). Poisoning due to pyrethroids. *Toxicological reviews*, 24(2), 93–106.
- [7] Hyland, C., & Laribi, O. (2017). Review of take-home pesticide exposure pathway in children living in agricultural areas. *Environmental research*, 156, 559–570.
- [8] Burr, S. A., & Ray, D. E. (2004). Structure-activity and interaction effects of 14 different pyrethroids on voltage-gated chloride ion channels. *Toxicological Sciences*, 77(2), 341–346.
- [9] Choi, J. S., & Soderlund, D. M. (2006). Structure–activity relationships for the action of 11 pyrethroid insecticides on rat Nav1. 8 sodium channels expressed in *Xenopus* oocytes. *Toxicology and applied pharmacology*, 211(3), 233–244.
- [10] Davies, T. G. E., Field, L. M., Usherwood, P. N. R., & Williamson, M. S. (2007). DDT, pyrethrins, pyrethroids and insect sodium channels. *IUBMB life*, 59(3), 151–162.
- [11] Schleier III, J. J., & Peterson, R. K. (2012). The joint toxicity of type I, II, and nonester pyrethroid insecticides. *Journal of economic entomology*, 105(1), 85–91.
- [12] Kauffmann, K., Gremm, L., Brendt, J., Schiwiy, A., Bluhm, K., Hollert, H., & Büchs, J. (2020). Alternative type of Ames test allows for dynamic mutagenicity detection by online monitoring of respiration activity. *Science of the Total Environment*, 726, 137862.
- [13] Maron, D. M., & Ames, B. N. (1983). Revised methods for the *Salmonella* mutagenicity test. *Mutation Research/Environmental Mutagenesis and Related Subjects*, 113(3–4), 173–215.
- [14] Mortelmans, K., & Zeiger, E. (2000). The Ames *Salmonella*/microsome mutagenicity assay. *Mutation research/fundamental and molecular mechanisms of mutagenesis*, 455(1–2), 29–60.
- [15] Dean, B. J., Brooks, T. M., Hodson-Walker, G., & Hutson, D. H. (1985). Genetic toxicology testing of 41 industrial chemicals. *Mutation Research/Reviews in Genetic Toxicology*, 153(1–2), 57–77.
- [16] Ames, B. N., Lee, F. D., & Durston, W. E. (1973). An improved bacterial test system for the detection and classification of mutagens and carcinogens. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 70(3), 782–786.
- [17] Flückiger-Isler, S., Baumeister, M., Braun, K., Gervais, V., Hasler-Nguyen, N., Reimann, R., ... & Engelhardt, G. (2004). Assessment of the performance of the Ames II™ assay: a collaborative study with 19 coded compounds. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 558(1–2), 181–197.
- [18] Merhi, M., Raynal, H., Cahuzac, E., Vinson, F., Cravedi, J. P., & Gamet-Payrastré, L. (2007). Occupational exposure to pesticides and risk of hematopoietic cancers: meta-analysis of case–control studies. *Cancer Causes & Control*, 18(10), 1209–1226.
- [19] Weichenthal, S., Moase, C., & Chan, P. (2010). A review of pesticide exposure and cancer incidence in the Agricultural Health Study cohort. *Environmental health perspectives*, 118(8), 1117–1125.
- [20] Imai, K., Yoshinaga, J., Yoshikane, M., Shiraishi, H., Mieno, M. N., Yoshiike, M., ... & Iwamoto, T. (2014). Pyrethroid insecticide exposure and semen quality of young Japanese men. *Reproductive Toxicology*, 43, 38–44.
- [21] Amweg, E. L., Weston, D. P., & Ureda, N. M. (2005). Use and toxicity of pyrethroid pesticides in the Central Valley, California, USA. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 24(4), 966–972.
- [22] Akyıl, D., Eren, Y., Konuk, M., Dere, H., & Serteser, A. (2017). Genotoxic evaluation of Halfenprox using the human peripheral lymphocyte micronucleus assay and the Ames test. *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 40(2), 191–195.

- [23] Özkara, A. (2022). Assessment of Mutagenic Activity of Karate Zeon Pesticide by Ames Test. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Fen Ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, 22(3), 465-469.
- [24] Kumar, A., Sharma, K., Tomar, M., Malik, V., & Kataria, S. K. (2013). Determination of mutagenic potential of imidacloprid in *Salmonella typhimurium*-TA 98 and TA 100 following bacterial reverse mutation assay. *International Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering Research*, 4(7), 703-710.
- [25] Foster, P. L., & Eisenstadt, E. (1985). Induction of transversion mutations in *Escherichia coli* by N-methyl-N'-nitro-N-nitrosoguanidine is SOS dependent. *Journal of bacteriology*, 163(1), 213-220.
- [26] Herrera, A., & Laborda, E. (1988). Mutagenic activity in synthetic pyrethroids in *Salmonella typhimurium*. *Mutagenesis*, 3(6), 509-514
- [27] Akintonwa, A., Awodele, O., Olayemi, S. O., Oreagba, I. A., & Olaniyi, O. M. (2008). The mutagenic testing of different brands of commonly used insecticides. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 7(13).
- [28] İla, H. B., Topaktas, M., Rencuzogullari, E., Kayraldiz, A., Donbak, L., & Daglioglu, Y. K. (2008). Genotoxic potential of cyfluthrin. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 656(1-2), 49-54.
- [29] Saleem, U., Ejaz, S., Ashraf, M., Omer, M. O., Altaf, I., Batool, Z., & Afzal, M. (2014). Mutagenic and cytotoxic potential of Endosulfan and Lambda-cyhalothrin—In vitro study describing individual and combined effects of pesticides. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 26(7), 1471-1479.
- [30] Özkara, A. (2017). Siperkor Pestisitinin Mutajenik Aktivitesinin Ames Testi ile Değerlendirilmesi. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Fen Ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, 17(2), 393-398.
- [31] Di Sotto, A., Evandri, M. G., & Mazzanti, G. (2008). Antimutagenic and mutagenic activities of some terpenes in the bacterial reverse mutation assay. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 653(1-2), 130-133.
- [32] Fishel, F. M. (2005). Pesticide Toxicity Profile: Synthetic Pyrethroid Pesticides: PI-54/PI091, 7/2005. EDIS, 2005(8).
- [33] Valles, S. M., & Koehler, P. G. (1997). Insecticides Used in the Urban Environment: Mode of Action: ENY282/IN077, 9/1997. EDIS, 1997.
- [34] Shafer, T. J., & Meyer, D. A. (2004). Effects of pyrethroids on voltage-sensitive calcium channels: a critical evaluation of strengths, weaknesses, data needs, and relationship to assessment of cumulative neurotoxicity. *Toxicology and applied pharmacology*, 196(2), 303-318.
- [35] Gajendiran, A., & Abraham, J. (2018). An overview of pyrethroid insecticides. *Frontiers in Biology*, 13(2), 79-90
- [36] Ross, M. K., Borazjani, A., Edwards, C. C., & Potter, P. M. (2006). Hydrolytic metabolism of pyrethroids by human and other mammalian carboxylesterases. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 71(5), 657-669.
- [37] Soderlund, D. M., Clark, J. M., Sheets, L. P., Mullin, L. S., Piccirillo, V. J., Sargent, D., ... & Weiner, M. L. (2002). Mechanisms of pyrethroid neurotoxicity: implications for cumulative risk assessment. *Toxicology*, 171(1), 3-59.
- [38] Kayaalp, O. (1995). *Tıbbi Farmakoloji*. Ankara: Hacettepe Taş Yayınları.
- [39] Öztaş, E. (2005). Bazı 9-sübstitüe fenantren türevlerinin mutajenik aktivitelerinin ames / salmonella / mikrozom testi ile araştırılması (Master's thesis, Anadolu University (Turkey)).
- [40] Ema, M., Imamura, T., Suzuki, H., Kobayashi, N., Naya, M., & Nakanishi, J. (2012). Evaluation of genotoxicity of multi-walled carbon nanotubes in a battery of in vitro and in vivo assays. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 63(2), 188-195.
- [41] Khambay, B.P. (2002). Pyrethroid insecticides. *Pesticide Outlook*, 13(2), 49-54

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